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Electrochemical Charge Transfer Effects of Detonation Nanodiamonds in Cortisol Immunosensor on Metal Electrodes

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ABSTRACT

Improving the detection of cortisol could enable daily health monitoring to prevent the onset and development of diseases caused by long-term exposure to stress. Electrochemical immunosensors enable easy preparation, high sensitivity and selectivity, rapid analysis and miniaturization without the need for complex equipment. Here, the effect of nanodiamonds on the voltammetric response of cortisol immunosensors with different metal electrodes is studied. Detonation nanodiamonds (DND) are deposited in various concentrations on gold and platinum working electrodes being part of a screen-printed electrode (SPE) sensor strip. Working electrodes with and without DNDs were functionalized by EDC/NHS, antibody, and bovine serum albumin incubation. Optical microscopy, scanning electron microscopy, infrared spectroscopy, and differential pulse voltammetry with ferri/ferrocyanide redox probe were used to analyze the sensor morphology and function. With ethanol pretreatment, the DND electrodes were robust during all processing steps. As little as 5% dilution of DND colloid was enough to affect the sensor functionality. During cortisol antigen detection, the Au or Pt reference sensors as well as DND/gold sensors exhibited DPV current decrease whereas DND/platinum sensors showed systematic current increase, indicating enhanced surface interaction or redox activity.

1 | Introduction

Cortisol, also known as the stress hormone and is responsible for many biological functions in the human body. Due to its function, the body can utilize energy from fats and proteins when needed. Cortisol also regulates glucose concentrations [1], suppresses inflammatory reactions, and the immune response so that the body does not lose energy. However, in the case of long-term high cortisol concentrations, it can have negative effects on health, weakening the immune system or increasing the risk of mental disorders [2].

Improving the detection of cortisol could prevent the onset and development of diseases caused by long-term exposure to stress and be a part of monitoring general health parameters of patients. Cortisol can be detected in blood, sweat, urine, hair, saliva, and tears [2, 3]. The concentration of cortisol in the blood changes during the day. The highest values are in the morning and then

decrease until the evening and the initial stage of sleep [2]. Typical range of cortisol concentration in blood serum in morning sampling (7–9 o'clock) is 118–618 nmol/L. In the afternoon sampling (13–17 o'clock) the values range from 85 to 460 nmol/L.

There are several laboratory methods for detecting cortisol, including immunochemiluminescent assay, enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay, high-performance liquid chromatography, liquid chromatography in tandem with mass spectroscopy (LC-MS/MS), surface plasmon resonance detection, radioimmunoassay, chemiluminescent immunoassay, and quartz crystal microbalance [1, 4]. These methods offer high sensitivity and specificity [4]. However, they are not practical for stress monitoring, as they are time-consuming, expensive and require laboratory instrumentation [1, 4]. The solution to these challenges can be development of cortisol point-of-care sensors (POCs).

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POCs applications have benefited from the use of screen-printed electrodes (SPE) for electrochemical measurements [1]. Electrochemical immunosensors enable easy sample preparation, offer high sensitivity and selectivity, rapid analysis without the need for complex equipment, and are suitable for miniaturization [5]. This all makes them cost-effective and ideal for portable and POC applications.

Depositing nanomaterials and nanocomposites onto the biosensor surface can generally increase the analytical capabilities, improve sensitivity, linear range, and lower the detection limit of analytes in biosensors [6]. This can be achieved by a higher surface area-to-volume ratio, by facilitating charge transfer, by novel mechanisms, and by the reduction of impedance at the electrolyte/electrode interface [7, 8]. The reduction of impedance leads to enhancement of the redox current and promotes the electron transfer rate, lowering the detection limit [7]. A high surface area-to-volume ratio amplifies the immunological reaction by providing a larger surface area for the immobilization of biorecognition molecules (such as antibodies), increasing the signal and thereby possibly the sensitivity of a biosensor [7, 8]. Various nanomaterials, including nanoparticles (diameter < 100 nm), carbon nanotubes, graphene oxide, and magnetic beads, can be deposited on the working electrode to achieve these goals and improve immunosensor performance in general [6].

In electrochemical biosensing studies, nanodiamonds have emerged as a promising material that can enhance immunosensors performance in detecting biomolecular targets by improving the electron transfer rate and increasing electrode surface area. Nanodiamond-based electrochemical biosensors were demonstrated for detection of various analytes in biological samples, including glucose, drugs, hormones, and others [9]. The benefits of adding at least some nanodiamonds to electrochemical immunosensors were recently shown. A voltammetric platform for immunosensing of a food allergen in peanuts via silver nanoparticles showed an improved response with some nanodiamonds dispersed on the electrode [10]. Carboxylated nanodiamonds mixed with gold nanoparticles as antibody anchors and immobilized on glassy carbon electrode provided the highest oxidation current in differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) for an immunosensor of breast cancer biomarker [11].

However, the electrode properties and interaction can vary significantly depending on the electrode composition, electronic properties, and structural arrangement. For instance, nanodiamonds or metal nanoparticles can assume different potentials (even 0.4 V) depending on the substrate they are deposited on [12].

The aim of this work was thus to study the effect of nanodiamonds on the voltammetric response of a cortisol immunosensor when different underlying metal working electrodes with or without nanodiamonds are used.

2 | Materials and Methods

Gold and platinum SPE were employed for the deposition of detonation nanodiamonds (DND) to compare the charge transfer effects in an electrochemical immunosensor assay for cortisol. SPE was part of the complete electrochemical sensor strip with circular screen-printed AgCl reference and counter electrodes

(BVT-AC1, BVT Technologies a.s.). The counter electrode was made from the same material as the working electrode. Preliminary screening showed that working electrodes with a 2 mm diameter had higher voltammetric peaks compared to 1 mm electrodes, thanks to their larger surface area, and their characteristics were more reproducible from batch to batch. Thus the data presented here are on 2 mm electrodes.

DND colloidal solution (4 nm, 2.5 w/v %, NanoCarbon Research Institute) was used in as-received form. Such DNDs exhibit positive zeta potential, hydrogen and oxygen surface chemical groups, sp² carbon phase, and low electrical conductivity [13, 14]. They were drop cast on the SPE (1 or 2 mm diameter) in various concentrations (using dilution in deionized water to 5%–50% concentration of the original DND stock solution) and biofunctionalized by EDC-NHS, antibody, and BSA incubation. An important step for stability and reproducibility was washing of SPE electrodes by ethanol (96% p.a.) prior to the DND dropcasting.

As shown in Supporting Information Figure S1, this protocol provided uniform coating by DND that was robust against further rinsing by deionized water. The key part was cleaning the electrodes with ethanol at first, which removed hydrocarbon adsorbates and other impurities that would prevent intimate contact between nanodiamonds and the electrodes. Optical microscopy images of SPE with Au and Pt working electrode after DND deposition (from 20% dilution), rinsing, biofunctionalization in PBS buffer solution, and cortisol antigen sensing steps in an assay buffer solution (Supporting Information Figure S2) confirmed the stability of the DND-coated electrode during all the processing and sensing steps. Even coatings from 5% of the original DND concentration were forming thin films and significantly lowered the electron transfer in comparison to the bare electrode. Nevertheless, 20% concentration was selected as optimal for continuous coating, good adhesion, and DPV response.

We assume that the robust adhesion of DND particles to gold and platinum surfaces can be attributed to the zeta potential (typically negative on gold and positive on nanodiamonds) and surface composition of nanodiamonds, which includes partially oxidized surface groups (–OH, –COOH) that promote electrostatic and van der Waals interactions with the native metal layer on Au and Pt electrodes. Additionally, during the drying process, capillary forces lead to compaction of the DND layer, further strengthening mechanical adhesion.

EDC-NHS chemistry was then used as a common method to couple biomolecules like proteins or antibodies to surfaces. EDC-NHS creates a reactive ester on a surface carboxyl group, which then can form a covalent bond with a primary amine group on a biomolecule. Thus, we assumed that such EDC-NHS chemistry can work also on DNDs and provide a link to antibodies. The EDC-NHS solution was prepared by adding 80 mg (0.4 M) of 1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)carbodiimide (EDC) and 11 mg (0.1 M) of N-hydroxysuccinimide (NHS), and this mixture was dissolved in 1 mL of PBS (pH = 7; 0.05 M). The EDC-NHS solution was used to activate terminal carboxylic groups by converting them into NHS esters, thereby improving the binding of subsequent layers [7]. Droplet of 2 μL of the EDC-NHS solution was applied to the electrode surfaces. After 90 min of spontaneous drying at room temperature, the working electrode was rinsed with deionized water to remove unbound material, and

the voltammetric characteristics were measured. After each measurement, the sensors were again lightly rinsed with deionized water.

Next, 2 μL of 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ mouse monoclonal anti-cortisol antibody solution in PBS (0.05 M, pH 7.0) was applied to the working electrode and left to incubate for 90 min at room temperature. Following incubation, CV and DPV measurements were performed. Then, 2 μL of 1% bovine serum albumin (BSA), was applied and spontaneously dried at room temperature for 1 h. BSA is commonly used in immunosensor assays as a blocking agent to minimize nonspecific adsorption of antibody on the sensor surface [5]. However, BSA is highly sensitive to washing and electrochemical measurement conditions. Performing electrochemical measurements after BSA coating without antigen addition can lead to partial removal or denaturation of the BSA molecules, affecting blocking efficiency and data reliability. Therefore, in accordance with protocols in literature, 2 μL of a hydrocortisone (cortisol) antigen solution (36.25 ng/mL), prepared by diluting a 1 mg/mL stock in methanol, was applied

directly onto the immunosensor after BSA to preserve the integrity and function of the BSA blocking layer. After 90 min incubation at a room temperature, a final voltammetric measurement was performed, and the sensor was cleaned and stored, to be eventually measured again.

The present study was primarily aimed at analyzing the effects on electrochemical response of the gold and platinum electrodes with nanodiamonds after EDC-NHS activation and antibody immobilization. The use of pristine cortisol solution was considered appropriate for such a study. Nevertheless, the cortisol immunoassay was based on the antibody/antigen complex validated in other studies including complex solutions and interference analysis. Our own validation experiments in artificial saliva on common screen-printed carbon electrodes also confirmed RSD recovery being 96%–105%. Thus, we expect that cortisol immunosensing in real clinical samples is feasible.

Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) was used to confirm the biofunctionalization process: 20 μL of the DND solution, DND/EDC-NHS, and DND/EDC-NHS/Ab was drop cast on

FIGURE 1 | Optical and SEM microscopic images of Au SPE sensors: (a,b) bare sensor with prior to DND deposition. (c,d) sensor after the DND deposition on the central working electrode. (e) FTIR spectra of DND before and after biofunctionalization with EDC-NHS and antibody (Ab).

Au-coated Si substrates at room temperature. We measured FTIR to verify formation of nanodiamond immunosensor with antibodies. FTIR was performed using a Thermo Nicolet iS50 spectrometer equipped with the KBr beam splitter and N₂-cooled MCT-HighD* detector. Specular apertured grazing angle reflectance method was used with an 80° incident light. An average of 128 scans per spectrum was collected at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ within the range of 4000–800 cm⁻¹. Bare Au substrate was measured as a background for baseline correction.

Optical and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) were used to characterize the resulting sensor morphologies. The setups are illustrated by the photograph in Supporting Information Figure S3. Optical microscope images were obtained with trinocular stereomicroscope ZEISS Stemi 508 equipped with ZEISS Axiocam 208 color camera (which was attached on top of the microscope), Zeiss Apo 1.5x FWD 53 mm front lens providing additional 1.5 magnification, and LED side illumination. ZEN software was used for acquiring the images. Color and dimensions were calibrated. The exposure time was set at 6.2 ms for all samples. Microscale surface morphology of the samples was obtained by SEM (Zeiss EVO 10). The SEM images were acquired at 20 kV acceleration voltage, 10 pA beam current, working distance of 10 mm, and magnifications up to 50 k in the secondary-electron (SE) regime using an off-beam detector.

EmStat Pico potentiostat (PalmSens) was used for the electrochemical analysis. The experimental setup is illustrated by the photograph in Supporting Information Figure S4. DPV regime was used as a commonly applied biosensor method, suppressing capacitive contributions and enhancing the charge transfer signal from the sensor. CV was employed for testing basic electrochemical performance characteristics. Measurements were performed using PSTrace software. CV was conducted five times for each sample to stabilize and thoroughly characterize the electrochemical behavior of the modified electrodes. Subsequently, DPV was performed for sensitive and quantitative analysis. This procedure ensured consistent and stable voltammogram readings, with the final CV measurement selected as the representative result. CV and DPV measurements were conducted within a potential range of -0.5 V to +0.7 V using a ferri/ferrocyanide redox probe (5 mM [Fe(CN)₆]^{3-/4-}, 250 mM KCl, 50 mM PBS, pH 7.0) to evaluate the effects of DND coatings, biofunctionalization steps, and the sensor's response to cortisol antigen. The scan rate was set at 0.1 V/s with a 10 mV step potential.

3 | Results and Discussion

The fabricated SPE sensors are illustrated on the case of Au working electrode by optical and SEM images in Figure 1. The optical image of SPE sensor prior to DND deposition shows clearly the central 2 mm Au working electrode surrounded by blue insulating paint and then by two concentric rings of AgCl reference electrode (gray) and Au counter electrode. Same structure is visible in SEM, however, the materials cannot be resolved in SE images. After the DND deposition, the working electrode becomes darker in the optical image. Without some DND remnants in the surroundings it would be difficult to notice though. Contrary, the SEM image now shows clear dark shade in the central area, contrasting with bright pristine Au counter electrode. Both optical and SEM images show rather homogeneous coating of the

working electrode by nanodiamonds. Optical microscopy images of SPE with Au and Pt working electrode after DND deposition, rinsing, bio-functionalization and cortisol antigen sensing steps are all shown in Supporting Information Figure S2. They illustrate consistent fabrication process and stability of the DND coated electrodes during all processing and sensing steps.

FTIR spectra of DND before and after biofunctionalization with EDC-NHS and antibody (Figure 1e) exhibit clear changes with new C–N, N–H, and C=O vibrational bands arising. They confirm successful biofunctionalization process. The gray curve represents the measurement of pristine DND, the blue curve corresponds to DND after EDC-NHS activation, and the green curve shows the measurement after antibody immobilization. Measurements after antigen binding were not performed, as BSA signal overwhelms the spectra. Characteristic peaks corresponding mainly to carboxylic acid (–COOH) groups and amide functionalities are identified in the FTIR spectra. The characteristic C=O stretching peak centered at ≈1720 cm⁻¹ in the pristine DND (gray) spectrum is indicative of carboxylic acid groups present on the nanodiamond surface. This peak is strong and sharp, confirming the presence of native –COOH groups essential for subsequent functionalization. It is accompanied by a broad O–H stretching band spanning ~2500–3300 cm⁻¹, characteristic of hydroxyl groups associated with –COOH moieties, and a broad O–H bending band around 1400–1450 cm⁻¹. Upon activation with EDC-NHS (blue spectrum), the C=O stretching peak at ~1720 cm⁻¹ disappears completely, indicating the full conversion of carboxyl groups into reactive intermediates. Concurrently, new amide I and amide II bands emerge around

FIGURE 2 | Typical electrochemical analysis profiles on Au electrode during DND deposition (from 20% dilution), biofunctionalization, and cortisol antigen sensing steps: (a) cyclic voltammetry—CV and (b) differential pulse voltammetry—DPV.

1650 cm^{-1} and 1550 cm^{-1} , respectively, confirming the formation of amide bonds during the functionalization process. Following antibody immobilization (green spectrum), there is a further increase in the intensity of the amide I and II bands, along with the broadening and enhancement of the N–H/O–H stretching bands in the 3200–3500 cm^{-1} region, consistent with the successful attachment of proteinaceous antibody molecules to the DND surface. FTIR spectra thus clearly prove the immunoassay formation.

Figure 2 shows typical results of electrochemical analysis on Au electrode after the DND deposition, biofunctionalization and cortisol antigen sensing steps. Cyclic voltammetry (Figure 2a) confirms standard behavior of the SPE platform during all processing steps. The CV profile is dominated by Faradaic contribution of ferrocyanine reduction and oxidation. However, it is difficult to resolve the details of current differences. DPV was thus used as the method of choice in electrochemical biosensors due to its higher sensitivity to detecting small surface and charge transfer changes as compared to CV. DPV (Figure 2b) shows typical profile that is predominantly characterized by the Faradaic contribution of the ferri/ferrocyanide redox couple, exhibiting a typical peak pattern associated with charge transfer processes. It resolves more clearly the different charge transfer currents related to each processing steps at expected potential value for ferri/ferrocyanine oxidation. One can clearly see that DPV peak current decreases after each steps. Such DPV spectra were collected for various combinations of working electrodes, DND concentrations, and

processing steps, comprising hundreds of data sets. For a comprehensive presentation of key results, we selected DPV peak currents in each functionalization and sensing step on the 2 mm gold and platinum working electrodes with 20% or 50% DND layers and performed relative comparison using the DPV current on the bare Au or Pt electrode as the reference.

Figure 3 plots the summary of mean values and standard deviations (as error bars) of the relative DPV current changes on gold and platinum SPE after a DND layer deposition (from 20% or 50% DND dilution) and after each biofunctionalization and antigen sensing step. The standard deviations seem relatively large. They are based on multiplicate experiments with variations of absolute values from sensor to sensor. Nevertheless, the data for both 20% and 50% nanodiamond loading, and also the individual data for each sample, show consistent trends. Actual values of CV and DPV peak currents in each functionalization and sensing step on the gold or platinum working electrodes with 20% or 50% DND layers made from 20% or 50% colloidal dilutions are available in Supporting Information Tables S2–S5. The relative response is calculated with respect to the initial DPV peak current on the respective bare metal electrode. Reference SPE sensor data without a DND layer are also shown for comparison. The arrows denote the trend of sensor response to antigen exposure.

Au reference sensor (Figure 3a,b) exhibits small decrease in DPV current during the biofunctionalization steps. That can be attributed to the EDC-NHS chemistry that is commonly used to attach biomolecules to gold surfaces for various applications, including

FIGURE 3 | Graphs summarizing mean values and standard deviation (as error bar) of relative DPV currents on SPE metal electrode after a DND layer deposition and after each biofunctionalization and antigen-sensing step (yellow). The relative response is calculated versus the initial DPV peak current on a bare metal electrode (100%). Reference SPE sensor data without a DND layer are also shown for comparison (green). The labels show actual percent value of the data point. The lines connect the data points as guide for an eye. The arrows denote the trend of sensor response to antigen exposure. The graphs are shown for: (a) 2 mm Au electrode with DND layer deposited from 20% dilution, (b) 2 mm Au electrode with DND layer deposited from 50% dilution, (c) 2 mm Pt electrode with DND layer deposited from 20% dilution, and (d) 2 mm Pt electrode with DND layer deposited from 50% dilution.

biosensors. During the sensing step the DPV current decreases by 12% which can be attributed to antigen binding. Thus the Au reference sensor can be considered as a standard immunoassay.

Adding nanodiamonds on the Au working electrodes decreases the DPV current more significantly. Such effect is commonly observed when some materials or molecules cover an electrode. It is attributed to the partial blocking of the conductive surface, which hinders redox probe access and slows the charge transfer. Then the DPV signal becomes stabilized during the biofunctionalization steps. Only for 50% DND, one can notice some DPV recovery which may be related to washing some DND from the surface. Yet in the optical microscope the observed change of coverage is negligible (Supporting Information Figure S2). In the sensing part of the DPV response, the current decreases by 8% on average. This is due to the binding between the Ag and immobilized Ab, forming a complex that further insulates the electrode surface and impedes electron flow. It is similar for both 20% and 50% DND coating and lower than the Au reference sensor. The DPV trend is similar though, as indicated by the arrows in Figure 3a,b. From the graph it seems that DNDs don't bring any significant benefit to Au SPE sensors in terms of DPV response.

The situation is rather different for the Pt SPE sensors. Pt reference sensor (Figure 3c) exhibits a clear increase in DPV current during the biofunctionalization steps. It seems that the biofunctionalization facilitates electron transfer with Pt electrode. Then in the sensing step the DPV current decreases, in agreement with common expectation that antigen blocks the charge transfer. The decrease is only 6%, which is about half of the Au SPE response. Most likely there is lower amount of antibodies as the EDC-NHS chemistry is not designed for Pt surfaces.

When DNDs are added on Pt SPE sensors, there is a usual decrease in DPV current. The decrease is more pronounced than on Au SPE in spite of same amounts of DND used. The reason must be thus more effective blocking of charge transfer due to additional Pt-DND electronic barrier [15]. However, in the sensing part of DPV response the current systematically increases, by 12% on average. This effect is clearly opposite to Au SPE sensor. One may suspect that the DPV increase is due to some DND being washed away during the antigen-binding step. However, optical microscope images do not indicate any noticeable change of coverage (Supporting Information Figure S2).

The opposite trend in DPV on Au/DND and Pt/DND electrodes during antigen sensing was observed systematically on all employed sensors and DND concentrations. It thus not a coincidence. Several phenomena can be considered that could lead to such effect.

It has been reported that nanodiamonds and nanodiamond layers can assume significantly different charge (by 0.4 V) on different substrates, including gold, platinum, or silicon, which showed an impact on photoluminescence as well as electron emission from the nanodiamonds [12, 15]. A different surface charge would be expected to shift the electrochemical reaction peak in DPV [16]. It was not observed in our case, though. Yet it could also lead to different molecular arrangements that can also influence electron emission from the same type of molecule as observed by correlative probe electron microscopy on thiorphan molecules [17]. Prior studies showed that antibody molecular assemblies can indeed increase secondary-electron

(SE) intensity [18, 19] whereas bacterial clusters showed a decrease in SE intensity.

Diamond materials can also act as emitters of solvated electrons under electrical bias or illumination [20]. Nanodiamond layers were shown not only to block but also facilitate charge (electron) transport when they were used as interlayers in organic photovoltaic devices [21]. There it was found that the most relevant factor is the energy level alignment, not nanodiamond doping. Energy level alignment represents a crucial parameter also for electrochemical charge transfer. Platinum may thus provide better energy alignment with nanodiamonds. However, in such a case the charge transfer should be increased already after DND deposition, not only in the sensing step when antigen (Ag) is captured on antibody (Ab). Moreover, gold has been demonstrated to provide better (even Ohmic) contact than platinum to nanodiamonds [15].

Specific molecular arrangement of Ag-Ab complexes is thus most likely the key part for the enhanced DPV currents on Pt/DND sensors. Similarly, donor-acceptor molecular complexes were observed to enhance charge transfer between B-doped diamond and electrolyte [22, 23]. Other simulations showed that hydrogen bonding through electron-donating hydroxyl groups can facilitate electron transfer, while the electron-withdrawing carboxyl group inhibits electron transfer across the junction to diamond [24]. On Pt electrodes, antigen-antibody/DND complex can also enhance electrolyte interaction and redox activity. When the antigen binds to the antibody immobilized on the electrode, it can bring a redox-active site close enough to the electrode to allow electron tunneling [25]. The antibody-antigen binding event also changes the local environment (e.g., steric hindrance, charge distribution), which affects the access of the redox mediator to the electrode [26]. Details of such a mechanism in the case of Ag-Ab/DND complex still remain to be investigated.

4 | Conclusion

The study demonstrated successful fabrication of SPE immunosensors for electrochemical cortisol detection using two different working electrode materials, gold and platinum. When the SPE was pretreated with ethanol, the DND coating on the SPE was homogeneous and robust against all washing and processing steps, as shown by optical and SEM. Various amount of DNDs was investigated using 5%–50% concentration of original DND stock solution (2.5 w/v%), where 20% was considered optimal for continuous coating, good adhesion, and DPV response.

The nanodiamond coatings consistently decreased DPV currents. The decrease was more pronounced for 50% DND, which can be explained by a thicker coating that has higher electrical resistance than 20% DND coating. Yet in all cases, the DPV current was not blocked, which indicated persistent charge transfer route through the DND coatings. The biofunctionalization of nanodiamonds with EDC-NHS and antibody was confirmed by further changes in voltammetric response and by FTIR spectra showing a clear fingerprint of biomolecules. During antigen detection there was a decrease in the DPV current on DND/gold whereas an increase was observed on DND/platinum sensors. It was systematic for various sensor sizes and DND concentrations. Reference gold or platinum electrodes without DND exhibited always a decrease in DPV current. As the molecules and DND

coatings were the same in all cases, the opposite DPV trend indicates different electrolyte–molecule–DND–electrode interaction which has an impact on the charge transfer.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data related with the manuscript are available upon request from the authors or online from the Zenodo repository (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15657328>).

References

1. L. Fiore, V. Mazzaracchio, A. Serani, et al., “Microfluidic Paper-Based Wearable Electrochemical Biosensor for Reliable Cortisol Detection in Sweat,” *Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical* 379 (2023): 2075–2082.
2. D. Y. Lee, E. Kim, and M. H. Choi, “Technical and Clinical Aspects of Cortisol as a Biochemical Marker of Chronic Stress,” *BMB Reports* 48 (2015): 209–216.
3. E. Dziurkowska and M. Wesolowski, “Cortisol as a Biomarker of Mental Disorder Severity,” *Journal of Clinical Medicine* 10 (2021): 5204.
4. A. Sharma, A. Wulff, A. Thomas, and S. Sonkusale, “Ultrasensitive Electrochemical Sensor for Detection of Salivary Cortisol in Stress Conditions,” *Microchimica Acta* 191(2024): 103.
5. F. S. Felix and L. Angnes, “Electrochemical Immunosensors – A Powerful Tool for Analytical Applications,” *Biosensors and Bioelectronics* 102 (2018): 470–478.
6. E. B. Aydin, M. Aydin, and M. K. Sezgin, *Advances in Clinical Chemistry* (Ed.: G. S. Makowski). Elsevier, 2019, pp. 1–57.
7. A. V. Police Patil, Y.-S. Chuang, C. Li, and C.-C. Wu, “Recent Advances in Electrochemical Immunosensors With Nanomaterial Assistance for Signal Amplification,” *Biosensors* 13 (2023): 125.
8. M. Ramesh, R. Janani, C. Deepa, and L. Rajeshkumar, “Nanotechnology-Enabled Biosensors: A Review of Fundamentals, Design Principles, Materials, and Applications,” *Biosensors* 13 (2023): 40.
9. L. R. G. Silva, J. H. S. Carvalho, J. S. Stefano, G. G. Oliveira, J. Prakash, and B. C. Janegitz, “Electrochemical Sensors and Biosensors Based on Nanodiamonds: A Review,” *Materials Today Communications* 35 (2023): 106142.
10. M. Freitas, A. Carvalho, H. P. A. Nouws, and C. Delerue-Matos, “Tracking Arachis Hypogaea Allergen in Pre-Packaged Foodstuff: A Nanodiamond-Based Electrochemical Biosensing Approach,” *Biosensors* 12 (2022): 429.

11. F. O. G. Olorundare, S. Makaluza, N. Midzi, O. A. Arotiba, and D. Nkosi, “A NanoDiamond/Gold Nanoparticle-Based Electrochemical Immunosensor for the Detection of HER 2 Cancer Biomarker,” *Biosensors and Bioelectronics: X* 18 (2024): 100483.
12. S. Stehlik, T. Petit, H. A. Girard, J.-C. Arnault, A. Kromka, and B. Rezek, “Nanoparticles Assume Electrical Potential According to Substrate, Size, and Surface Termination,” *Langmuir* 29 (2013): 1634–1641.
13. V. N. Mochalin, O. Shenderova, D. Ho, and Y. Gogotsi, “The Properties and Applications of Nanodiamonds,” *Nature Nanotech* 7 (2012): 11–23.
14. S. Stehlik, O. Szabo, E. Shagieva, et al., “Electrical and Colloidal Properties of Hydrogenated Nanodiamonds: Effects of Structure, Composition and Size,” *Carbon Trends* 14 (2024): 100327.
15. S. Stehlik, L. Ondic, A. M. Berhane, et al., “Photoluminescence of Nanodiamonds Influenced by Charge Transfer from Silicon and Metal Substrates,” *Diamond and Related Materials* 63 (2016): 91.
16. R. Chetty, V. P. Singh, A. Madhusudhan, et al., *Functional Smart Nanomaterials and Their Theranostics Approaches* (A. Madhusudhan, S. D. Purohit, R. Prasad, and A. Husen) (Springer Nature, 2024), pp. 241–261.
17. E. Ukraintsev, H. Hematian, J. Neuman, and B. Rezek, *Proceedings of the 15th International Conference on Nanomaterials - NANOCON* (2023): 360–367.
18. Q. Zhang, M. Zhang, Y. Du, et al., “Trace Detection of SARS-CoV-2 N-Protein by Diamond Solution-Gate Field-Effect Transistor,” *Diamond and Related Materials* 134 (2023): 109775.
19. T. Ogura, and J. Qiu, “High-Contrast Observation of Unstained Proteins and Viruses by Scanning Electron Microscopy,” *PLoS ONE* 7 (2012): e46904.
20. A. Chemin, I. Levine, M. Rusu, et al., “Surface-Mediated Charge Transfer of Photogenerated Carriers in Diamond,” *Small Methods* 7 (2023): 2300423.
21. A. S. Djoumessi, A. Scharwardt, D. Miliaieva, et al., “Nanodiamonds as Charge Extraction Layer in Organic Solar Cells: The Impact of the Nanodiamond Surface Chemistry,” *Solar RRL* 7 (2023): 2201061.
22. D. López-Carballeira, J. Raymakers, A. Artemenko, et al., “Effect of Oligothiophene Spacer Length on Photogenerated Charge Transfer From Perylene Diimide to Boron-Doped Diamond Electrodes,” *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells* 248(2022):111984.
23. J. Raymakers, H. Krysova, A. Artemenko, et al., “Functionalization of Boron-Doped Diamond With a Push–Pull Chromophore via Sonogashira and CuAAC Chemistry,” *RSC Advances* 8 (2018): 33276.
24. A. Olejnik, B. Dec, W. A. I. Goddard, and R. Bogdanowicz, “Hopping or Tunneling? Tailoring the Electron Transport Mechanisms Through Hydrogen Bonding Geometry in the Boron-Doped Diamond Molecular Junctions,” *Journal of Physical Chemistry Letters* 13 (2022): 7972.
25. H. Chen, O. Simoska, K. Lim, et al., “Fundamentals, Applications, and Future Directions of Bioelectrocatalysis,” *Chemical Reviews* 120 (2020): 12903.
26. X. Wang, J. Zhou, and H. Wang, “Bioreceptors as the Key Components for Electrochemical Biosensing in Medicine,” *Cell Reports Physical Science* 5 (2024): 101801.

Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section. **Supporting Figure S1.** Optical microscopy images of SPE electrodes on Au after DND and water rinsing in the case: a) without surface pre-treatment, b) after ethanol washing. The insets show different resulting SEM surface morphology of the sensors. **Supporting Figure S2.** Optical microscopy images of SPE with Au and Pt working electrode after DND deposition (from 20% dilution),

rinsing, bio-functionalization and cortisol antigen sensing steps. **Supporting Figure S3.** Photographs of a) SEM machine Zeiss EVO 10, b) SEM sample holder with SPE sensors, and c) optical microscope Zeiss Stemi 508 with Axiocam 208 color camera and LED illumination in our laboratory. **Supporting Figure S4.** Photograph of the experimental cortisol sensor setup using SPE with deposited nanodiamonds and EmStat pico USB potentiostat. **Supporting Table S1.** Example of one set of electrochemical analysis: CV and DPV currents on Au and Pt working electrodes in 2 mm size before and after deposition of DNDs from various dilutions (5-100%), in quadruplicates. **Supporting Table S2.** CV and DPV peak currents on 2 mm gold working electrodes (in quadruplicates) with 20% DND layer after each step of functionalization. **Supporting Table S3.** CV and DPV peak currents on 2 mm gold working electrodes (in quadruplicates) with 50% DND layer after each step of functionalization. **Supporting Table S4.** CV and DPV peak currents on 2 mm platinum working electrodes (in quadruplicates) with 20% DND layer after each step of functionalization. **Supporting Table S5.** CV and DPV peak currents on 2 mm platinum working electrodes (in quadruplicates) with 50% DND layer after each step of functionalization.